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UDC 338.2:378:316.32

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TARASENKO O. S.**Methodological foundations of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization**

The subject of the research is the theoretical and methodological foundations of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization.

The aim of the research is to determine the methodological foundations for the formation of a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization.

Research methods. The study used both theoretical and practical methods: analysis of scientific literature; method of comparative analysis; conceptual method; SWOT analysis; systematic approach; scenario analysis; factor analysis; graphical, tabular methods, etc.

Results of the investigation. It has been established that in the context of globalization, higher education institutions should integrate into the global economic system, while maintaining the stability of their functioning and ensuring long-term sustainable development. It is proved that the economic development of higher education institutions, as part of the overall development strategy of Ukraine, is a critical aspect for their existence. The main aspects of globalization that affect the economic development of higher education institutions are identified, namely: technological progress; international mobility; transformation of the labor market. The key principles of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions are identified: international competitiveness; innovation and technological development; partnership with the private sector; flexibility and mobility; sustainability and human resource development. The main economic factors that influence the sustainable development of higher education institutions are investigated: diversification of funding sources; internationalization of educational programs; innovative development. The factors of positive impact (international cooperation and mobility; integration into the international market of educational services; development of technologies and distance education; expanding access to knowledge; internationalization of educational programs) and negative impact (increased competition; depopulation and brain drain; financial dependence; uneven access to technology; cultural and language barriers), which in the process of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions create both opportunities and threats for the further development of higher education institutions, are analyzed and identified. The criteria for the effectiveness of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions are determined: economic efficiency; quality of educational services; innovation potential; international integration; social responsibility and sustainability; organizational flexibility and managerial efficiency; information and digital infrastructure. It is proved that these criteria will allow to comprehensively assess the effectiveness and efficiency of the economic development strategy of a higher education institution in the context of globalization, ensuring compliance with the modern requirements of the international educational community and the market of educational services. In the process of developing and further implementing an effective strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions, taking into account global educational trends, the following approaches, methods and mechanisms have been proposed: systematic approach; modeling of economic processes; integration of innovative approaches; diversification of income sources; international approach; innovative development; partnership with business. It is proved that a reasonable choice and

further effective implementation of the economic development strategy of a higher education institution requires constant monitoring and evaluation of results, including systematic analysis of the achieved indicators, identification of deviations and implementation of corrective actions.

Scope of the results. *Management of higher education institutions, financing and economics of education, internationalization of education, educational policy and reform of the education system, digitalization of education, development of research activities.*

Conclusions. *Thus, in the context of globalization, higher education institutions face new challenges and opportunities dictated by the need to strategize their economic development. Formulating an economic development strategy that takes into account current educational trends and global factors is an important step to ensure their stability and competitiveness. An effective economic development strategy of a higher education institution should take into account such aspects as diversification of income sources, internationalization, innovative development and cooperation with business. The application of these approaches will allow higher education institutions not only to survive in the face of increased competition, but also to become leaders in their field at the global level. The methodological foundations for the formation of a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization provide for a comprehensive approach to the development and implementation of principles and mechanisms that take into account the main global trends and the specifics of the functioning of higher education institutions. The developed strategy of economic development of higher education institutions should primarily comply with the principles of flexibility, adaptability and be focused on achieving the goals of sustainable development of higher education institutions in a rapidly changing environment.*

Keywords: *methodological foundations, strategy, economic development, higher education institutions, globalization, education financing, innovative approaches, international competition, strategic development, internationalization of education, economic efficiency, adaptation to global challenges, integration into the world educational space.*

ПУЗИРЬОВА П. В.
ТАРАСЕНКО О. С.

Методологічні основи формування стратегії економічного розвитку закладів вищої освіти в контексті глобалізації

Предметом дослідження є теоретичні та методологічні основи формування стратегії економічного розвитку закладів вищої освіти в контексті глобалізації.

Метою дослідження є визначення методологічних основ формування стратегії економічного розвитку закладів вищої освіти в контексті глобалізації.

Методи дослідження. При дослідженні використовувались, як теоретичні так і практичні методи: аналіз наукової літератури; метод порівняльного аналізу; концептуальний метод; SWOT-аналіз; системний підхід; сценарний аналіз; факторний аналіз; графічний, табличний методи та ін.

Результати роботи. Встановлено, що в умовах глобалізації ЗВО мають інтегруватися в глобальну економічну систему, залишаючи при цьому стабільність свого функціонування та забезпечуючи довготривалий сталий розвиток. Доведено, що економічний розвиток ЗВО, як частина загальної стратегії розвитку України, є критично важливим аспектом для їхнього існування. Визначено основні аспекти глобалізації, що впливають на економічний розвиток ЗВО, а саме: технологічний прогрес; міжнародна мобільність; трансформація ринку праці. Визначено ключові принципи формування стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО: міжнародна конкурентоспроможність; інноваційність та технологічний розвиток; партнерство з приватним сектором; гнучкість та мобільність; сталість і розвиток людських ресурсів. Досліджено основні економічні чинники, які впливають на сталий розвиток ЗВО: диверсифікація джерел фінансування; інтернаціоналізація освітніх програм; інноваційний розвиток. Проаналізовано та визначено чинники позитивного впливу (міжнародна співпраця та мобільність; інтеграція в міжнародний ринок освітніх послуг; розвиток технологій та дистанційна освіта; розширення доступу до знань; інтернаціоналізація навчальних програм) та не-

гативного впливу (збільшення конкуренції; депопуляція та «відтік мізків»; фінансова залежність; нерівномірний доступ до технологій; культурна та мовна бар'єрність), які в процесі формування стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО створюють як можливості, так і загрози для подальшого розвитку ЗВО. Визначено критерії ефективності формування стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО: економічна ефективність; якість освітніх послуг; інноваційний потенціал; міжнародна інтеграція; соціальна відповідальність та стійкість; організаційна гнучкість та управлінська ефективність; інформаційна та цифрова інфраструктура. Доведено, що дані критерії дозволять всебічно оцінити ефективність та результативність стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО у контексті глобалізації, забезпечуючи відповідність сучасним вимогам міжнародної освітньої спільноти та ринку освітніх послуг. В процесі розробки та подальшої імплементації ефективної стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО з урахуванням глобальних освітніх трендів було запропоновано такі підходи, методи і механізми: системний підхід; моделювання економічних процесів; інтеграція інноваційних підходів; диверсифікація джерел доходів; інтернаціональний підхід; інноваційний розвиток; партнерство з бізнесом. Доведено, що обґрунтований вибір та подальша ефективна імплементація стратегії економічного розвитку ЗВО потребує постійного контролю та оцінки результатів, що включає систематичний аналіз досягнутих показників, виявлення відхилень і запровадження коригуючих дій.

Галузь застосування результатів. Управління ЗВО, фінансування та економіка освіти, інтернаціоналізація освіти, освітня політика та реформування системи освіти, цифровізація освіти, розвиток науково-дослідницької діяльності.

Висновки. Отже, в умовах глобалізації ЗВО стикаються з новими викликами та можливостями, продиктованими необхідністю стратегування їх економічного розвитку. Формування стратегії економічного розвитку з урахуванням сучасних освітніх тенденцій та чинників глобального характеру є важливим кроком для забезпечення їхньої стабільності і конкурентоспроможності. Ефективна стратегія економічного розвитку ЗВО повинна враховувати такі аспекти, як диверсифікація джерел доходів, інтернаціоналізація, інноваційний розвиток та співпраця з бізнесом. Застосування цих підходів дозволить ЗВО не лише вижити в умовах посиленої конкуренції, але й стати лідерами у своїй галузі на глобальному рівні. Методологічні основи формування стратегії економічного розвитку закладів вищої освіти в умовах глобалізації передбачають комплексний підхід до розробки та впровадження принципів і механізмів, що враховують основні глобальні тенденції та специфіку функціонування ЗВО. Розроблена стратегія економічного розвитку ЗВО повинна першочергового відповідати принципам гнучкості, адаптивності та бути орієнтованою на досягнення цілей сталого розвитку ЗВО у швидкозмінному середовищі.

Ключові слова: методологічні основи, стратегія, економічний розвиток, заклади вищої освіти, глобалізація, фінансування освіти, інноваційні підходи, міжнародна конкуренція, стратегічний розвиток, інтернаціоналізація освіти, економічна ефективність, адаптація до глобальних викликів, інтеграція у світовий освітній простір.

Formulation of the problem. Globalization is one of the key trends in the modern development of the world economy, where higher education institutions (HEIs) face obstacles related to increased competition, changes in the financial environment and the need to adapt to the new conditions of the global knowledge market. In the context of globalization, higher education institutions have to integrate into the global economic system while maintaining the stability of their operations and ensuring long-term sustainable development. The economic development of higher education institutions, as part of the overall development strategy of Ukraine, is becoming a critical aspect for their existence. In

this regard, the issue of determining the methodological basis for the formation of an economic development strategy that will allow them to effectively adapt to the conditions of globalization and ensure their sustainable development is relevant.

Analysis of research and publications on the problem. The issue of methodological foundations for forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization is quite relevant and diverse. Many scholars from different fields of knowledge have worked and continue to work on this topic: economics, pedagogy, management and education. Some well-known scholars who have contributed to the

development of this issue are: Peter Drucker – raised the issue of the development of institutions, including educational institutions, in the context of global changes, and emphasized the importance of innovation and flexibility of management in the context of globalization; Zygmunt Bauman – studied the impact of globalization on various aspects of social life, including education; Michael Porter – explored concepts that can be used to analyze the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of global competition; W. Edward Deming – known for his work on the development of the global economy. Edwards Deming – known for his works on quality management, which are important for the organizational development of educational institutions, especially in the context of global competition; Simon Marginson – focuses on changes in the higher education system under the influence of globalization, raises the issue of economic and social equality in education; Yuriy Surmin and Valeriy Hrynev – studied economic and managerial aspects of the development of the higher education system in Ukraine, in particular in the context of reforms and global changes; Jean-Claude Juncker – often covered topics related to the development of education in Europe in the context of globalization and European integration. These and other scholars have made a significant contribution to the development of methodological approaches to managing the economic development of higher education institutions, especially in the context of globalization.

Presenting main material. Globalization affects all spheres of social life, including the higher education system. Higher education institutions face new challenges and opportunities associated with changes in the global economy, technological progress, mobility of students and academic staff, and growing competition in the international market of educational services [1; 3; 6; 8; 12; 15].

Globalization is a multifaceted process that includes economic, social, cultural, political and other aspects. From the perspective of higher education economics, globalization changes not only the structure of financing and management of higher education institutions, but also affects academic mobility, competition for students and teachers, and the internationalization of curricula. Changing economic conditions at the global level necessitate the adaptation of traditional models of higher education management and financing. The integration of high-

er education institutions into global educational and research processes poses challenges to them in the form of unstable financial flows, which requires diversification of income sources and development of new economic models [2; 5; 9; 17; 21].

Globalization has significantly changed the context in which HEIs operate, due to the internationalization of education, increased mobility of students and teachers, and increased competition between HEIs in the international market of educational services. The main manifestations of globalization in terms of their impact on the economic development of higher education institutions are:

- technological progress – digitalization and innovative technologies that change traditional models of education and management of educational processes;
- international mobility – a growing number of students and teachers participating in international academic mobility programs (changes the structure of demand for educational services);
- transformation of the labor market – rapid changes in the global economy that require higher education institutions to quickly adapt their educational programs to the needs of the labor market [4; 7; 10; 13].

Taking into account the main trends in higher education, national problems of HEI development in the context of a full-scale war on the part of the Russian Federation, the methodological basis for forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization should take into account the existing potential, the state of the external environment (a system of factors that contribute to development and factors that form an array of threats and to which the higher education institution must adapt) and criteria that will allow to assess the achieved level of efficiency and effectiveness. This necessitates substantiation of the system of principles, study of factors and determination of criteria for evaluating the effectiveness of the chosen strategy. Thus, important criteria for such models include ensuring the sustainability of the financial base of higher education institutions, increasing their competitiveness at the global level, and supporting innovative processes in education and research [11; 14; 16; 20].

The following principles should be considered as the key principles in formulating the strategy of

economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization:

- the principle of international competitiveness – HEIs should introduce and implement educational programs and research projects that meet international standards and attract students from different countries;
- principle of innovation and technological development – integration of innovative technologies into the educational process and research activities contributes to improving the quality of education and attractiveness of higher education institutions for foreign students and investors;
- the principle of partnership with the private sector – cooperation with business and industry allows higher education institutions not only to receive funding, but also to orient educational programs to the needs of the labor market;
- principle of flexibility and mobility – exchange programs for students and teachers, as well as the possibility of obtaining double degrees, promote international integration and attract foreign investors;
- principle of sustainability and development of human resources – ensuring sustainable development of intellectual capital through improving the management system, developing human resources and improving the quality of education.

These principles are aimed at effectively shaping the strategy of economic development and competitiveness of higher education institutions in the context of globalization, preserving their reputation and attractiveness in the international arena.

One of the key aspects of formulating a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions is to identify the main economic factors that affect the sustainable development of higher education institutions, including:

- diversification of funding sources – includes attracting both public funding and private investment, international grants and charitable contributions;
- internationalization of educational programs – expansion of international cooperation and mobility of students and teachers, which helps to attract additional funds and improve the quality of education;
- innovative development – creation of new educational and scientific products and services that have commercial value and that will allow the HEI to increase revenues and improve its competitiveness.

Also, in the process of formulating the strategy of economic development of higher education institu-

tions, it is advisable to take into account the impact of positive and negative factors that both create opportunities and pose threats to the development of higher education institutions (Table 1) [18; 19; 21].

So, globalization creates many opportunities for the development of higher education institutions, but also creates certain obstacles that require the development of strategic approaches to overcome them. Optimal development of higher education institutions in a globalized world depends on the effective use of positive factors and minimization of negative ones [15–19].

The criteria for assessing the effectiveness of formulating a strategy for economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization can be divided into several groups focused on different aspects of activity:

1. Economic efficiency:

- revenue growth (assesses the growth of the HEI's own revenues, such as tuition fees, grant revenues, revenues from research activities and partnership programs);
- investment attraction (effectiveness of investment attraction, including international funds, financing programs and corporate sponsorships);
- cost optimization (reduction of operating expenses, increase of efficiency of resource use, in particular through the introduction of digital technologies).

2. Quality of educational services:

- improving academic reputation (positions of higher education institutions in international and national university rankings);
- raising the level of students (results of admission campaigns, number of foreign students, success of graduates in the labor market, their career growth and social mobility);
- international accreditation and partnerships (availability of double degree programs, international research projects, and partnerships with other HEIs).

3. Innovation potential:

- development of research activities (number and quality of scientific publications, patents, innovative developments, participation in international research consortia);
- introduction of innovations in the educational process (the degree of integration of modern technologies, teaching methods and scientific results into the curriculum);

Table 1. The system of global factors of positive and negative impact in the context of the formation and implementation of the economic development strategy of higher education institutions

Positive factors		Negative factors	
International cooperation and mobility	Globalization opens up access to new partnership programs, faculty and student exchanges, and joint research projects, which helps improve the quality of education and the international ranking of higher education institutions	Increased competition	Competition for students, teachers, and financial resources is growing globally. Less developed higher education institutions may not be able to withstand this competition, losing their positions in the education market
Integration into the international market of educational services	HEIs can attract foreign students, which increases revenues and raises the global prestige of the university	Depopulation and “brain drain”	Globalization promotes the migration of talented students and teachers to countries with better educational systems, which can weaken internal resources of higher education institutions and negatively affect their development
Digitalization of the educational process	Digital technologies allow to expand the audience of students through online courses, distance learning and other new educational formats, which contributes to economic optimization and reduction of physical infrastructure costs	Financial dependence	HEIs may become dependent on international grants and funding, which entails risks of losing independence in strategic decision-making
Expanding access to knowledge	Globalization increases access to scientific literature, research, and innovation, which can improve the quality of teaching and research base of higher education institutions	Uneven access to technology	Not all HEIs have equal opportunities to implement the latest technologies, which leads to unequal conditions in the educational space
Internationalization of educational programs	Universities can integrate international standards into their curricula, which increases their competitiveness in the global market	Cultural and language barriers	Internationalization can lead to the loss of national identity of educational programs and systems, as well as to difficulties in adapting foreign students and teachers to new cultural conditions

- cooperation with business (creation of innovation centers, business incubators, technology parks on the basis of higher education institutions).

4. International integration:

- internationalization of educational programs (number of programs implemented in English, exchange of students and teachers, participation in international conferences and educational projects);
- ranking and branding of the HEI (positioning in international rankings such as QS World University Rankings or Times Higher Education, perception in the international market of educational services);
- level of foreign students and teachers (number of students and teachers from other countries, which contributes to the increase of international activity and development of cross-cultural competencies).

5. Social responsibility and realization of the third mission of the university:

- public benefit and impact on the community (contribution of the university to the development of the local community through social programs, community activities and job creation);
- environmental sustainability (development and implementation of energy efficiency policies and environmental initiatives that meet the principles of sustainable development);
- participation in global initiatives (activity in international programs and initiatives on sustainable development, environmental responsibility, humanitarian aid, etc.).

6. Organizational flexibility and management efficiency:

- adaptability to global changes (ability to quickly adapt to global trends in the education sector, change strategies and institutional priorities);
 - innovative management methods (introduction of new management models, including digital platforms for managing resources, students and academic processes);
 - attracting qualified personnel (support for the professional development of employees, advanced training, and engagement of international experts).
7. Information and digital infrastructure:
- development of IT infrastructure (degree of automation of management processes, availability of a modern educational platform that provides access to online courses and distance learning);
 - digitalization of research and education (use of modern digital tools in research, teaching and interaction with students) [4–11].

These criteria will allow for a comprehensive assessment of the effectiveness and efficiency of the economic development strategy of a higher education institution in the context of globalization, ensuring compliance with the modern requirements of the international educational community and the educational services market.

In the process of developing and further implementing an effective strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions, taking into account global educational trends, it is advisable to take into account the following approaches, methods and mechanisms, which are summarized in Table 2 [6–13].

Thus, the general process of forming a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization from the methodological side will look like this (Fig. 1) [9–15].

Table 2. Methodological principles of forming an effective strategy of economic development of higher education institutions taking into account global educational trends

№	Approach	Description.
1	Systematic approach	The systemic approach involves the integration of all aspects of the HEI's activities, including educational, scientific and economic components, into a single management system.
2	Modeling of economic processes	Modeling of economic processes is a key stage in the development of conceptual models of HEI development, where the use of econometric models, simulation modeling and system dynamics allows forecasting the development of educational institutions under different scenarios, which will provide a comprehensive analysis of economic and financial indicators, including income from educational activities, grants, international projects, etc.
3	Integration of innovative approaches	Given the significant technological changes, it is important to include innovative approaches, such as digitalization of educational processes, introduction of distance learning, and use of big data for management decision-making, in the conceptual models of economic development of higher education institutions, which will increase the efficiency of managing the resources of higher education institutions and adapt to new market requirements.
4	Diversification of income sources	One of the main challenges faced by HEIs in the context of globalization is dependence on a single source of funding, usually the state. To ensure stability, it is necessary to diversify financial flows, which involves attracting alternative sources of income: international grants, sponsorships, commercialization of research, creation of partnerships with businesses, etc.
5	International approach	Internationalization is an important strategy for the development of higher education institutions, which includes attracting international students, program exchange, double degree programs, and participation in international educational and research projects, which provides access to global resources and enhances the reputation of higher education institutions on the world stage.
6	Innovative development	Innovation is a key factor for the sustainable development of higher education institutions, where the development of innovative educational programs and the commercialization of research contribute not only to financial growth but also create new opportunities for international cooperation and improvement of the quality of education.
7	Partnership with business	Public-private partnerships are a promising area for the development of higher education institutions, where universities can cooperate with businesses to create innovative products, conduct joint research and implement projects that can generate significant revenue.

Fig. 1. Formation of a strategy for economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization

An important task that needs to be addressed in the process of formulating an effective economic development strategy for higher education institutions is to study the conditions and factors of the external global environment, assess opportunities and threats, and the resource potential of each individual higher education institution. For example, internationalization and innovation development strategies can be effectively applied in higher education institutions that have high scientific potential and active international relations. One example of the successful application of such strategies is the partnership between the HEI and international organizations, such as the European Union and the World Bank, which provide financial support to HEIs working on educational and research projects aimed at ensuring sustainable development. A well-founded choice and further effective implementation of the economic development strategy of a higher education institution requires constant monitoring and evaluation of results, including systematic analysis of the indicators achieved, identification of deviations, and implementation of corrective actions [13–19].

Conclusions

Thus, in the context of globalization, higher education institutions face new challenges and opportunities dictated by the need to strategize their economic development. Developing an economic development strategy that takes into account current educational trends and global factors is an important step to ensure their stability and competitiveness. An effective economic development strategy of a higher education institution should take into account such aspects as diversification of income sources, internationalization, innovative development and cooperation with business. The application of these approaches will allow higher education institutions not only to survive in the face of increased competition, but also to become leaders in their field at the global level. The methodological framework for formulating a strategy for the economic development of higher education institutions in the context of globalization provides for a comprehensive approach to the development and implementation of principles and mechanisms that take into account the main global trends and the specifics of the functioning of higher education institutions. The developed strategy of economic development of higher education institutions

should primarily comply with the principles of flexibility, adaptability and be focused on achieving the goals of sustainable development of higher education institutions in a rapidly changing environment.

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